

Terms of Reference for the CMIP Data Node Operations Team (CDNOT)

A CMIP Data Node Operations Team shall be appointed by the WGCM Infrastructure Panel (WIP) and will include representatives from groups responsible for CMIP data nodes.

The CDNOT is charged with implementing a federation of data nodes responsive to the requirements of the evolving CMIP process as articulated by the WIP.

The CDNOT scope covers functions and resource issues (hardware, networks, people) related to: installing, configuring and operating all the nodes and node services in the CMIP data federation and the policies and processes involved in both managing data on a data node (including acquisition, quality assurance, citation, versioning, and publishing) and providing access services.

Within this scope, the CDNOT shall be responsible for:

1. Providing formal input to the WIP with regard to data node operations, resource issues, and other concerns related to meeting WIP requirements.
2. Providing formal input to any software providers as to software requirements and constraints arising from the operational environment/experience.
3. Maintaining documentation outlining the required resources, configuration and mandatory access services on a data node.
4. Agreeing how to configure federation-level services and service nodes to support WIP requirements.
5. Where necessary, establishing a timetable and methodology for federation-wide software migrations, upgrades or configuration changes.
6. Drafting and maintaining documentation to share problems and solutions related to the deployment, configuration and operational management of CMIP data nodes.
7. Drafting and maintaining guidelines describing how the CMIP data management plans should be implemented on data nodes (e.g. to cover how identifiers should be obtained and used, metadata requirements, quality control and the addition and removal of data with versioning).
8. Monitoring for compliance the implementation of the CMIP data management plans across the federation, and providing feedback to the WIP.